

Role of preprints in scholarly communication on COVID-19: A quantitative survey of medRxiv and bioRxiv

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Introduction

Preprints, i.e., papers that are published before submission to journals, can allow researchers to share their research results quickly. In the 2010s, various preprint hosting sites emerged, including bioRxiv [operated by Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory (CSHL) since 2013] and medRxiv (operated by CSHL, Yale University, and BMJ since 2019). Intensive research began on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), which was declared a pandemic by the WHO in many countries. Medical care for patients with COVID-19 required up-to-date results from preclinical and clinical studies, and thus, preprints were used to quickly share research results on COVID-19 (Brierley et al., 2022). Preprints also shortened the peer review period, leading to the widespread distribution of new scholarly communication (Tsunoda et al., 2020, 2022). This study aims to clarify the role of preprints in scholarly communication on COVID-19 on medRxiv and bioRxiv.

Materials and Method

COVID-19 preprints were defined based on the subject classifications of medRxiv and bioRxiv (hereinafter, M&B). Preprint metadata from January 2020 to December 2022 were collected using the application programming interface (API) of M&B. Because preprints can be revised and updated by authors and may have multiple versions with revision dates marked for each time they have been revised, this study focused on the first version of each article. The proportion of COVID-19 preprints was defined as the share of the number of COVID-19 preprints to the number of all preprints (expressed as a percentage). The publication rate was defined as the rate at which the publisher's DOI was assigned to the preprints (expressed as a decimal).

Results

Figure 1 shows the proportion of COVID-19 and non-COVID-19 preprints in the medRxiv and bioRxiv. The number of M&B preprints doubled from 2,881 in January 2020 to 5,879 in May. It then

decreased to 4,338 in August but remained around 4,000. M&B had 37 (1%) COVID-19 preprints of the total preprints in January 2020, which increased to 1,961 (33%) in May 2020. Thereafter, the number of submissions dropped to 308 (8%) in December 2022. The breakdown of this change is as follows. In medRxiv, there were 7 (3%) COVID-19 preprints in January 2020, which increased rapidly to 1,625 (78%) in May 2020 and then decreased to 206 (25%) in December 2022. In bioRxiv, there were 30 (1%) COVID-19 preprints in January 2020, which increased rapidly to 336 (9%) in May 2020 and then decreased to 102 (3%) in December 2022.

Figure 1. Proportion of COVID-19 preprints in M&B

Table 1 shows the status of the top four journals that had papers published from M&B. In most journals, the proportion of COVID-19 preprints in medRxiv was greater than 50%, whereas the proportion of COVID-19 preprints in bioRxiv was less than 10%.

Table 1. Top four M&B journals

	Journal	Paper	COVID-19	non-COVID-19	(%)
medRx	<i>PLoS One</i>	1,225	834	391	68
	<i>Sci Rep</i>	608	370	238	61
	<i>BMJ Open</i>	504	276	228	55
	<i>Nat Commun</i>	349	231	118	66
bioRx	<i>Elife</i>	2,340	43	2,297	2
	<i>Nat Commun</i>	2,099	139	1,960	7
	<i>PLoS One</i>	1,896	87	1,809	5
	<i>Sci Rep</i>	1,580	108	1,472	7

Figure 2 shows changes in the number and proportion of COVID-19 papers over time in the top four journals described in Table 1. The number of papers published in all journals shows a decreasing trend. *PLoS One* on medRxiv, *Sci Rep* on medRxiv, *BMJ Open* on medRxiv, *Nat Commun* on bioRxiv, *PLoS One* on bioRxiv, and *Sci Rep* on bioRxiv showed a downward trend, but *Nat Commun* on medRxiv and *Elife* on bioRxiv did not show a downward trend. Trends varied by journal.

Figure 2. Top four M&B journals

Figure 3 shows the rate of publication of M&B. It is revealed that the publication rate of M&B increased with time. The majority of preprints were published after approximately 18 months. It is shown that throughout 2020–2021, the publication rate remained around 50% (bioRxiv) and around 60% (medRxiv). Although no significant differences were observed, the publication rate of M&B during 2020–2021 for COVID-19 preprints was higher than the publication rate of non-COVID-19 preprints. A further survey needs to be conducted to trace the trend after 18 months.

Figure 3. Publication rates of M&B

Conclusion and Discussion

Our study showed that between 2020 and 2022, M&B received a certain number of submissions. In particular, during the first half of 2020, the rate of COVID-19 preprints increased rapidly, from 37 (1%) in January 2020 to 1,961 (33%) in May 2020. After the declaration of the COVID-19 pandemic, quick sharing of results from research studies was required to assist hospital staff with diagnosis and treatment, and many researchers published their research results on COVID-19 in preprints; this is supported by our data. The environment of the peer review process also changed, prioritizing peer review of COVID-19 preprints (Sullivan et al., 2022) with improved peer review processes (Paul, Brody & Geppert, 2021). When new academic hotspots, like the COVID-19 pandemic, suddenly appear, researchers need a platform to share their results. This quantitative survey revealed that preprints grasped academic hotspots and played an important role in the immediacy of scholarly communications.

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